

Synthesis of Some New 2-(N-Substituted Carboxamidomethyl Thio)-5-Phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and Related Compounds

H. A. EL-SHERIEF, A. G. GHATTAS, A. M. MAHMOUD and A. E. ABDEL-RAHMAN

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt, A. R. E.

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A series of new 2-(N-substituted carboxamidomethyl thio)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (I and II) were prepared. Reaction of 3-chloromethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione with heterocyclic mercaptans and tertiary amines gave 3-S-substituted mercaptomethyl-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (IV) and 3-(N-aminomethyl-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione chloride (V) respectively. Structures of the resulting products have been ascertained by their elemental and spectral data. The biological activities of the synthesized compounds were screened against some bacteria.

In view of analgesic and anticonvulsant activities of oxadiazoles^{1,2} and simple amides^{3,4}, we undertook the synthesis of 2-(N-substituted carboxamidomethyl thio)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (I, II) hoping that these compounds may exhibit enhanced activity than the parent compounds.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. Elemental analysis was carried on a Colman C and H analyser model 29. IR spectra were run on a Unicam SP 1000 Infrared Spectrophotometer. UV absorption spectra determined by Unicam SP 1750 Ultraviolet Spectrophotometer. The microbiological screening was carried out by Dr. Abd El-Gaffar, Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine, Assiut University.

2-(N-Substituted carboxamidomethyl thio)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles, I and II: 5-Phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (0.005 mole)⁵ was dissolved in 15 ml of 10% alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution. To this was added 0.007 mole of N-chloroacetyl derivatives of aromatic amines or 2-aminothiazoles with constant stirring for 2 hr at 80°. It was left overnight and the solid that crystallised was filtered and washed. Recrystallisation from ethanol gave the corresponding products, yield not less than 70% (cf. Table 1).

3-S-Substituted mercaptomethyl-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione, (IVa-h): To a solution of benzoxazole-2-thiol (0.007 mole) in 15 ml of 10% alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution was added 0.005 mole of 3-chloromethyl-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 min.

TABLE 1—2-(N-SUBSTITUTED CARBOXAMIDOMETHYL THIO)-5-PHENYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES I and II

Comp. No.	m.p. °C	Mol. Formula	Calcd./Found			
			O	H	N	S
Ia	198-99	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	61.73	4.18	13.50	10.28
			61.22	4.26	13.41	10.11
b	174-75	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ SBz	49.23	3.07	10.76	8.20
			49.61	3.12	10.41	8.11
c	169-70	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ SOI	55.57	3.47	12.15	9.26
			55.21	3.31	12.27	9.02
d	208-204	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	58.71	3.97	12.84	9.78
			58.11	3.76	12.91	10.03
e	159-54	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	59.82	4.39	12.31	9.38
			59.71	4.11	12.41	9.52
f	144-45	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	62.76	4.61	12.92	9.84
			62.33	4.41	12.81	9.76
g	188-84	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	61.18	4.24	11.89	9.06
			60.82	4.28	11.21	9.41
h	238-39	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	57.46	3.66	11.83	9.01
			57.48	3.41	11.28	9.54
i	221-22	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	53.93	3.37	13.48	8.98
			54.04	3.11	13.81	8.61
j	134-35	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	62.76	4.61	12.92	9.84
			62.46	4.24	12.71	9.38
k	157-58	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	66.48	4.15	11.63	8.86
			66.78	4.48	11.30	8.64

(Table 1 Contd.)

l	185-86	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ S	57.69	3.84	15.98	10.25
			57.48	3.62	15.35	10.02
m	190-91	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ S	57.69	3.84	15.98	10.25
			57.49	3.81	15.61	10.11
n	246-47	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	55.43	3.26	15.21	17.39
			55.61	3.21	15.64	17.81
o	204-205	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₂ S	59.85	4.51	16.62	7.60
			59.77	4.16	16.45	7.08
IIa	259-60	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	49.05	3.14	15.09	20.12
			48.68	3.11	15.41	20.54
b	203-204	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	57.86	3.55	14.21	16.24
			57.71	3.46	14.12	16.71
c	209-210	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	56.60	4.77	13.20	15.09
			56.41	4.34	13.49	15.31
d	217-18	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	58.82	3.92	13.72	15.68
			58.61	3.64	13.21	15.94
e	243-44	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ S ₂ O ₄	51.15	4.04	14.14	16.16
			51.02	4.20	14.31	16.70

TABLE 2—3-S-SUBSTITUTED MERCAPTOMETHYL-5-PHENYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOL-2-THIONE(IV) AND 3-(N-AMINOMETHYL)-5-PHENYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOL-2-THIONE CHLORIDES(V)

Comp. No.	m.p. °C	Mol. Formula	Calcd./Found			
			O	H	N	S
IVa	161-62	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	56.30	3.22	12.31	18.76
			56.41	3.02	12.61	18.21
b	205-206	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ S ₂ O	53.78	3.08	11.76	26.89
			53.21	3.12	11.29	26.72
c	144-46	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂ O	56.47	3.52	16.47	18.82
			56.46	3.41	16.07	18.34
d	150-52	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	61.38	3.32	10.74	16.36
			61.46	3.11	10.51	16.26
e	290-92	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	50.95	2.76	8.91	20.38
			50.84	2.61	8.82	20.86
f	136-38	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	52.84	3.10	14.50	16.58
			52.48	3.21	14.24	16.44
g	201-202	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂ Cl	50.68	2.73	13.91	15.90
			50.51	2.67	13.81	16.02
h	152-53	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ S ₂ O	53.12	3.12	14.58	25.00
			53.41	3.41	14.46	25.61
Va	244-46	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ SOCl	54.99	3.92	13.74	10.47
			54.76	3.81	13.41	10.81
b	224-26	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SOCl	56.33	4.38	13.14	10.01
			56.16	4.21	13.61	10.21
c	199-200	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SOCl	60.75	3.93	11.81	9.00
			60.41	3.81	11.61	9.42
d	234-36	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SOCl	60.75	3.93	11.81	9.00
			60.48	3.87	11.64	9.61

It was left overnight and the solid obtained was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. The other compounds in this series were prepared similarly in 60-70% yields and are listed in Table 2.

3-(N-Pyridinomethyl)-5-phenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione chloride (V): 3-Chloromethyl-5-phenyl-1, 3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (1 g, 0.005 mole) in dry pyridine (5 ml) was refluxed for 5 min, cooled and filtered. The solid was crystallised from methanol to give (Va). Compounds Vb-d were prepared accordingly (cf. Table 2).

Results and Discussion

The present report deals with the preparation of some new 2-(N-substituted carboxamidomethyl thio) oxadiazoles (I and II), 3-S-substituted merca-

ptomethyl oxadiazol-2-thione (IV) and substituted 3-N-aminomethyl oxadiazol-2-thione chlorides(V).

The 5-phenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione was prepared by the method of Young and Wood⁵. N-Chloroacetyl derivatives of substituted aniline, 2 and 3-aminopyridine, 4,5-disubstituted 2-aminothiazoles, 2-aminobenzthiazole and 4-aminophenazone were prepared following the method of Jacobs⁶. The ethanolic solution of N-(substituted) 2-chloroacetamides condensed with 5-phenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione in alcoholic alkali produced 2-N-(aryl) carboxamidomethyl thio-1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles (Ia-k), 2-N (pyridyl)-carboxamidomethyl thio-1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles (I l, m), 2-N (2'-benzthiazolyl) carboxamidomethyl thio-1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles (In), 2-N (1'-phenyl-2', 3'-dimethyl-2'-pyrazolin-5-one-4'-yl) carboxamidomethyl thio-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol(Io) and 2-N (2'-thiazolyl) carboxamidomethyl thio-1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles(IIa-e).

I

Ar	Ar
a ; phenyl	j ; benzyl
b ; <i>p</i> -bromophenyl	k ; β -naphthyl
c ; <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	l ; 2-pyridyl
d ; <i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	m ; 3-pyridyl
e ; <i>p</i> -anisyl	n ; 2-benzothiazolyl
f ; <i>p</i> -tolyl	o ; 1-phenyl-2,3-dimethyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one-4-yl
g ; <i>p</i> -acetylphenyl	
h ; <i>p</i> -carboxyphenyl	
i ; <i>p</i> -nitrophenyl	

II

R	R'
a ; H	H
b ; H	phenyl
c ; H	<i>p</i> -anisyl
d ; H	<i>p</i> -tolyl
e ; carboethoxy	methyl

The ir spectra of the compounds I and II exhibited two bands at 1680-1660 cm^{-1} and 3320-3290 cm^{-1} characteristic for (C=O) and (-NH) respectively. The structure of compounds I and II was proved by their uv absorption being similar to those of 2-S-alkyl derivatives⁷, in showing the characteristic absorption band at 268-275 nm.

Furthermore, 3-chloromethyl-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (III) was prepared by the method of Vakula and Srinivasan⁷. The reaction of III with 2-benzoxazolethiol, 2-benzimidazolethiol, 2-benzthiazolethiol, naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-2-thiol, naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-2-thiol-5-sulphonic acid, 5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione, 5-*p*-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione and 5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-thione in 10% alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution gave the corresponding 3-S-substituted mercaptomethyl-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione derivatives (IVa-h) respectively.

1630-1640 cm^{-1} assigned to C=S and C=N stretching frequencies respectively.

III reacted with tertiary amines (pyridine, α -picoline, quinoline and isoquinoline) to give the corresponding 3-(N-aminomethyl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione chlorides (V) (Table 2) in high yields.

The ir spectra of Va-d show a characteristic band of C=S and C=N as sharp peaks at 1300-1330 cm^{-1} and at 1635-1650 cm^{-1} respectively.

Antimicrobial activities : The antibacterial activities of compounds Ia, c, e, h, i, l, n ; IIa, c, e, o ; IIIa, b, c, e, h, o and IVa, b, c, e, h were tested *in vitro* against a variety of microbes⁸ including Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria such as, *S. aureus*, *Pyogenes*, *E. coli* and *P. morgani*. There was no inhibitory activity against *Pyogenes* and a

X
IVa ; O
b ; NH
c ; S

R
IVd ; H
e ; SO ₂ H

X	R
IVf ; O	H
g ; O	Cl
h ; S	H

R
Va ; (N-pyridino)chloride
b ; (N- α -picolino)chloride
c ; (N-quinolino)chloride
d ; (N-isoquinolino)chloride.

The ir spectra of compounds IVa-h were characterised by strong bands at 1300-1330 cm^{-1} and

little to a strong activity against the other microorganisms at $10^{-6}M$. The compounds more active (more than 60% inhibition) against *S. aureus* are Ic, l, IIe, c,

IIIb and IVa, against *E. coli* are Ic, IIIc, h and against *P. morganii* is IVe.

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